

INFLUENCE OF POLYPHENOL EXTRACT, EXTRACTED FROM THE PLANT QUICE (CYDONIA OBLONG), ON THE mitoK_{ATP}-CHANNEL OF THE RAT'S LIVER

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Abstract. *In this article, the effect of PF-4 polyphenol extracts isolated from quince (Cydonia oblong) on the ATP-dependent potassium channel in rat liver mitochondria was studied. In the experiments, PF-4 polyphenol extracts (5 µg/ml, 10 µg/ml, 15 µg/ml, 20 µg/ml) activated the ATP-inhibited mitoK_{ATP} channel. The obtained results make it possible to create drugs with membrane-active action of PF-4 polyphenol extract in the future.*

Keywords: *(Cydonia oblong), mitochondrial membrane, mitoK_{ATP} channel, PF-4 polyphenol extract, ATP.*

Introduction

Modern biomedical science has proven that the development of various pathologies is associated with functional changes in mitochondria. In this case, the role of mitochondrial subunits, in particular the mitoK_{ATP} channel, is of particular importance.

The mitoK_{ATP} channel also participates in the normal course of cell physiology and the stability of mitochondrial volume. Currently, a number of modulators regulating the mitoK_{ATP} channel have been identified, and the mechanisms of their influence on channel function have been sufficiently studied [1,2,3]. The function of the mitoK_{ATP} channel is to ensure the entry of K⁺ ions into the mitochondrial matrix. It is assumed that the entry of K⁺ ions from the mitoK_{ATP} channel into the matrix is in a slowed state, and K⁺ ions are transported through ion diffusion from the membrane [4,5].

Currently, the field of medicine and pharmacology considers the mitoK_{ATP} channel as an important object in conducting test experiments to study the medicinal properties of biologically active substances [6]. It also indicates the possibility of correction of mitoK_{ATP} channel dysfunction with pharmacological agents in various pathologies [7,8, 9].

The development of some pathological conditions is based on processes associated with mitochondrial dysfunction or hypoxia. The role of the mitoK_{ATP} channel in mitochondria in the origin and development of pathological processes has been identified [10]. It has been proven that the mitoK_{ATP} channel participates in the normal course of mitochondrial physiology, the stability of mitochondrial volume [11], and the adaptation of the body to various extreme influences [12].

In accordance with the foregoing, the identification of natural compounds that effectively influence the function of the mitoK_{ATP} channel and the study of their mechanisms of action is currently of fundamental and practical importance.

For this purpose, we studied the influence of PF-4 polyphenol extract isolated from quince (*Cydonia oblong*) plants on the activity of rat liver mitoK_{ATP} channels under in vitro conditions.

Purpose of the research

Is to study the activating effect of PF-4 polyphenol extract isolated from quince (*Sydonia oblong*) on the mitoK_{ATP}-channel of rat liver mitochondria.

Research methods and materials

The experiments were conducted under in vitro conditions on white outbred male rats weighing 180-200 g. The animals were fed under standard laboratory conditions (temperature 20-24°C, humidity 65%, and sufficient water and feed). Experiments on animals were used in accordance with the Helsinki International Declaration, the Council of the International Organization of Medical Sciences (SIOMS), and the “regulations on the bioethics of the use of laboratory animals in scientific research” approved by the Institute of Biophysics and Biochemistry of the National University of Uzbekistan (Report of 22.02.2019).

Isolation of mitochondria from rat liver. Separation of mitochondria from rat liver was carried out by differential centrifugation. After opening the rat's abdominal cavity, the liver was isolated and placed in a pre-prepared cooled separatory medium. The composition of the separation medium is as follows: sucrose - 250 mM, tris-HCl - 10 mM, EDTA - 1 mM 7,4 [13]. The rat liver is homogenized and centrifuged in two stages, and the resulting pellet is mixed with 250 mM sucrose, 10 mM Tris-HCl solution in a 10:1 ratio and stored in an ice container [14].

Determination of mitoK_{ATP} channel activity. The kinetics of mitochondrial swelling (0,3-0,4 mg/ml) was determined by recording the change in optical density at a wavelength of 540 nm [15] on a UV-5000 spectrophotometer in an open cell (volume 3 ml) at 26°C and constantly stirred.

The following incubation medium was used to determine the permeability of the mitochondrial membrane: 125 mM KCl, 10 mM Hepes, 5 mM succinate, 1 mM MgCl₂, 2,5 mM K₂HPO₄, 2,5 mM KH₂PO₄, 0,005 mM rotenone and 0,001 mM oligomycin, pH 7,4 [4]. The swelling rate of mitochondria was determined when the protein content in the medium was 0,3 mg/ml. Statistical processing of the obtained results and drawing of images were carried out using the US computer program OriginLab 8.6.

Obtained results and their analysis

The mitoK_{ATP} channel is important as a selective potassium channel, its permeability to K⁺ ions is inhibited in the presence of ATP. This process is useful in experimental studies of the cardioprotective effect of substances.

In addition to ATP, sulfonyleurea preparations also have an inhibitory effect on the mitoK_{ATP} channel. In particular, activators (diazoxide, chromocalin, nicorandil) and inhibitors (ATP, glibenclamide) of the activity of the mitoK_{ATP} channel were identified. Therefore, an in-depth study of the mechanisms of regulation of mitoK_{ATP} channel activity is of scientific and practical importance [10].

In our experiments, initially, the permeability of the mitoK_{ATP} channel was observed normally under conditions where only intact mitochondria were inserted (intact mitochondria). We marked these results as 100%. Adding 200 μM of ATP to the incubation medium reduced the ionic permeability of the mitoK_{ATP} channel by 21,5±2,6 compared to the initial intact state (Fig. 1).

PF-4 polyphenol extract, isolated from quince (*Cydonia oblonga*), also exhibited a specific activating effect on the mitoK_{ATP} channel. In the experiments, the activating effect of PF-4 polyphenol extract at concentrations of 5, 10, 15, and 20 µg/ml on the mitoK_{ATP} channel was observed up to 86,2% (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. A) Permeability of the rat liver mitoK_{ATP} channel under the influence of PF-4 polyphenol extract (original diagram). Note: on the ordinate axis - the permeability of the mitoK_{ATP} channel, on the abscissa axis - the duration of the experiment (t= seconds).

PF-1 B) activating effect of polyphenol extract on rat liver mitoK_{ATP}-channel (histogram).

Note: on the ordinate axis - the permeability of the mitoK_{ATP} channel is expressed as a percentage, on the abscissa axis - the concentrations of PF-1 extract are given. n=7, *P<0,05, **P<0,01; ***P<0,001.

The permeability of the mitoK_{ATP} channel at a concentration of 5 µg/ml of PF-4 polyphenol extract was 31,1±3.4%, which activated the mitoK_{ATP} channel by 9,6% compared to the control (+ATP) state. Increasing the concentration of PF to 10, 15, and 20 µg/ml during the experiment activated the mitoK_{ATP} channel by 32,1%, 52,1%, and 64,8% compared to the control. Under these conditions, the permeability of the mitoK_{ATP} channel was 53,6±3,8, 73,6±2,5, and 86,3±2,9, respectively, under the influence of concentrations of 10<20 µg/ml in intact mitochondria.

In the above experiments, the activating effect of PF-4 polyphenol extract on the rat liver mitoK_{ATP} channel was scientifically proven.

MitoK_{ATP} channels are activated under conditions of hypoxia, ischemia, and reperfusion. Their activation is part of cellular defense mechanisms. Since the 1997 discovery that activation of the mitochondrial ATP-sensitive K⁺channel (mitoK_{ATP}) protects the heart from ischemic/reperfusion (I/R) damage, the important role of mitochondrial intramembrane K⁺ permeability in cytoprotection has been illustrated in numerous models[16]. In our experiments, the influence of polyphenolic extracts on the mitoK_{ATP} channel in vitro was also studied. Polyphenols are natural antioxidant compounds that help protect cells from oxidative stress and ischemic damage[17]. The studied polyphenols influence the structure of potassium channels in the mitochondrial membrane, stimulating their opening. It can contribute to the normal functioning

of mitoK_{ATP} channels by reducing the level of respiratory chain enzymes (Complex I) -dependent ROS formation in the inner mitochondrial membrane.

In scientific sources, some biologically active substances, for example, some types of hormones, are important as metabolic regulators of the mitochondrial potassium channel, some sex hormones beta-estradiol and testosterone have an activating effect on the mitoK_{ATP} channel, while the male sex hormone testosterone, along with activating the mitoK_{ATP} channel, also exhibits a cardioprotective effect. Thus, although the nature of the origin of biologically active substances is close to each other, the mechanism of their action on the same cellular structure is different or the probability of their proximity is high. Therefore, an in-depth study of the function of the mitoK_{ATP} channel and the mechanisms of its regulation under the influence of pharmacological agents allows us to determine the specifics of the pharmacological action of biologically active substances.

Conclusion: Thus, in conclusion, it can be said that the activating effect of the mitoK_{ATP} channel of PF-4 polyphenol extracts isolated from quince (*Cydonia oblong*) can be used in the future for the effective treatment of cardiovascular diseases, circulatory system, and liver diseases.

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